

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: IROEZINDU****FIRST NAME: MICHAEL****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

RUDIMENTS OF EFFECTIVE ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

There have been several starting points in the course of my long-spanning academic pursuit. Over these years, I can only recall few scheduled periods I was convincingly taught how to start my academic writing on a solid pedestal, gradually build up balanced content while maintaining a persuasive tone. Akin to the recipe for a delicious meal, the ACA-401 coursepack for period one provides the background information for effective and persuasive academic writing. Various ingredients that make for a beautiful product are carefully mixed in a comprehensive manual. Additionally, there is a fifteen-minute informational video that details EUCLID's requirements and key steps including the use of approved Microsoft Word template, a standardized pattern of file naming, and the various styles employed in writing a paper. The coursepack left me in no doubt about the high standards expected of EUCLID's students as they navigate through their academic writing experiences for response papers, major papers, and indeed thesis. I found the coursepack and the video quite complementary. While most students can grasp the rudiments of effective academic writing by a careful sojourn through the coursepack, attempting to write a response paper without watching the video could prove to be a difficult expedition. With these carefully packaged rudiments, I cannot ask for a better way to be introduced to a promising academic career as a doctoral student at EUCLID.

2) A PERSUASIVE AND BALANCED APPROACH

EUCLID starts by exposing the student to essay writing. From the get-go, it underscores the importance of using evidence-based information to persuade readers (EUCLID 2019, 1). In doing this, a key step is to figure out a question or task around which the response should be built (ibid.). Based on the question or task, I learned the importance of mapping out an essay plan that captures the key terms that need to be critically analyzed. In the process of organizing the ideas, it is only natural to progress from the known to the unknown. If one is fortunate to have rich experience with the topic, the initial draft of the essay might have a reasonable flow. As one begins to take a deeper dive, the need to research around the issue at stake becomes glaring. I realized that building up a persuasive essay is not as simple as driving down a straight road. In the search for credible academic sources to support my argument, it becomes obvious that I must possess the skill of balancing divergent views as well.

This is similar to the process I often go through to arrive at a clinical diagnosis as a physician. When the patient first presents to my clinic, after the pleasantries, the very first task is to determine the patient's chief complaint(s). Based on my basic knowledge of medicine, I would review the entire symptoms of the patient and conduct a systematic physical examination to arrive at a list of possible diagnoses. As I review the symptoms and examine the patient, I realize that disease may present in various ways and different ailments may have some symptoms in common. This pushes me into the realm of critical thinking to unravel the most likely diagnosis. As I critically review the list of possible diagnoses, I have to acknowledge what makes each diagnosis possible while trying to identify the very thing that makes any an unlikely diagnosis. Opening up to the views of my team members brings in various perspectives. As I go through these motions, I draw on my past experiences, the experiences of other physicians and in some cases I may have to embark on further research to arrive at a logical clinical diagnosis.

Similar to my experience in clinical care, the need to modify the initial draft of the essay becomes obvious after a few days of reviewing and thinking through the write-up. The second essay plan often has advantages over the first especially after including ideas from the notes compiled while reading. Whenever I have cause to review my clinical diagnosis on a patient, I never lose track of the chief complaint for which the patient presented to me. Similarly, keeping the essay question in mind as the essay is edited helps the writer to stay focused (EUCLID 2019, 3). As my patient begins to respond to treatment, I will always ask myself if I have provided appropriate and broad-based care for the ailment. Besides, I try to verify if I have followed the guidelines for the management of such ailments. When the illness in question presents with obvious difficulties, a balanced and logical approach to the treatment is always gratifying. At such moments, I liken the things I learned about essay writing and handing in an essay to discharging my patient after a thorough, balanced, and logical clinical care.

3) AVOID PLAGIARISM

Academic writing could be a demanding and time-intensive exercise. In the process of developing one's work, borrowing ideas from writers who are experienced in the field is inevitable. The EUCLID period-one coursepack provides me with ample warning about the dangers of borrowing ideas from other sources without according well-deserved credit to the authors. Why should I acknowledge my source? Failure to mention the source of the information constitutes plagiarism. Considering that discoveries and solutions to some global challenges depend on research and communication of research findings to the end-users, plagiarism can even hinder the drive to confront challenges through academic writing (Orluwene and Magnus-Arewa 2020, 31). At EUCLID, plagiarism is considered a serious academic offense that could attract severe punishments (EUCLID 2019, 5).

The coursepack painstakingly outlined steps to avoid plagiarism. Based on the guidelines provided, citations and quotations are very useful in avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 6). Quotations help to convey ideas in the exact ways they have been shared by the originator. While short quotations can be captured using quotation marks within a paragraph, the recommendation is that longer quotations, which often span over four lines, should be indented without quotations marks (EUCLID 2019, 7). Although the use of quotations is appropriate, I understand that it is preferable to limit the number of quotations in my academic writing by expressing the borrowed idea in my own words which is the principle of paraphrasing (EUCLID 2019, 6). I further observed that avoiding many quotations in my essay should not make me settle for sentences that are just close paraphrases of the source (EUCLID 2019, 16). From a physician's perspective, acceptable paraphrasing is like taking the pains to adapt a previously described treatment approach to the peculiar circumstances of my ailing patient without altering the essence of the "borrowed" treatment approach. During the weekly review meeting, while taking delight in the adaptation of the treatment approach, it is only ethical that I acknowledge the originator of the regimen. The course resources also provide clear information on how to cite authors. I learned about in-text citations and listing of works cited. In-text citation enables the writer to cite the author(s) in the text of the paper by putting the authors' name, year of publication, and page number in parenthesis (EUCLID 2019, 6). Nevertheless, I learned about situations where citing a source becomes unnecessary. The rule of thumb is that there is no need to cite your source if the information in question is generally known (EUCLID 2019, 10). With this insight, I feel well equipped to strike a balance between a relatively free-flowing style of writing and pausing to acknowledge my sources.

4) STYLE IS KEY

I am not a stranger to style in academic writing. As a supervisor of postgraduate doctors of the West African College of Physicians (WACP), I am required to have the WACP guidelines and recommended style by my fingertips. The WACP recommends the use of Vancouver style. Any research proposal or dissertation which does not follow the approved guidelines will be considered ineligible. In contrast, my Master of Public Health (MPH) degree program was based on the Harvard style which incidentally I have scarcely

used since graduation. At EUCLID, the Chicago Manual of Style (Turabian) or sometimes other internationally recognized rules are recommended for academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 24). This is my first experience with the Turabian style. So far, I have noticed it has similarities with the Harvard style. Although I will have to forgo my longstanding romance with the Vancouver style while at EUCLID, my regard for the importance of style and my previous experience with the Harvard style will be key to a potentially successful adventure with the Turabian style. Moreover, I am delighted to understand from the crib sheet that some basic rules of writing cut across all styles. For example, the Turabian like other styles I have used, recommends that every acronym should be written out in full the first time it is used (EUCLID 2019, 44). Subsequently, the acronym should be used.

Considering that I have been accustomed to other styles, one might wonder if I might inadvertently be involved in occasional scenarios of combining different styles in my papers. While that seems to be a potential risk, I am confident that I shall rigorously scrutinize my work to ensure consistent use of the Turabian style. There is precedence worth mentioning. After completing my MPH thesis based on the Harvard style, I went through the rigors of re-writing sections of the work using the Vancouver style which unfortunately was the recommended style by the peer-reviewed journals we were targeting for publication of our findings. Such rigor will prove extremely helpful during my academic writing activities at EUCLID.

5) SOME DEGREE OF LIBERTY

As I familiarized myself with the whole idea of being guided by the rules, it dawned on me that things are not always cast in stone in academic writing. Like poetic license, I understood from the coursepack that there are few occasions when experienced writers could deviate from the norm to achieve free-flow, distinction and meet the satisfaction of their audience (EUCLID 2019, 25). While I plan to abide by the recommended guidelines, I certainly will savor opportunities when I could interweave the fabrics of my writing skills with the recommended style(s). The extent to which I might be privileged to benefit from the liberty that seems exclusively reserved for creative writers remains to be seen.

6) OBSERVATIONS: EXCEPTIONS TO THE RULE

The guide provided by the available resources is quite commendable. Nevertheless, I observed some things that could be potentially confusing. The decision to place an apostrophe before or after the “s” when indicating possession easily comes to mind. Although the apostrophe rule is unequivocal regarding possessive singular or plural nouns, it seems a bit ambiguous in circumstances where it is determined by the pronunciation of the word as in the case of the name “Louis.” The possessive form Louis’s seems recommended if the name is pronounced “Loo-is” while Louis will be more suitable if it is pronounced “Loo-ie” (EUCLID 2019, 18). I was thrilled to realize the intricate differences between standard British English (SBE) and standard American English (SAE). However, in a few instances, I struggled with the grammatical relevance of the distinction. For

example, I did not see much relevance in the difference between their use of large collective nouns. The good thing is that I can choose between SBE and SAE as long as consistency is maintained.

Unless a writer becomes accustomed to the use of internet terminology, it is very easy to continue to ponder whether to use them uppercase without a hyphen (as in the case of “Web cam”) or spelled lowercase and closed without a hyphen (as in the case of “webcam”). If I set out to religiously adhere to the guidance of not mixing numbers and symbols, how on earth am I supposed to know that 45 percent is permissible while I am expected to consistently write 45° or forty-five degrees? So, in learning the rules, I understood that it is probably as important to appreciate the exceptions to the rules. Talking about exceptions, I was left wondering whether the use of in-text referencing for the work by Gerson and Gerson on pages 6 and 7 of the coursepack without a comma between the authors and the page number was an exception to the rule or a typographical error (EUCLID 2019, 6-7). Based on the Turabian style, I can hardly see this as an exception to the rule. Therefore, it is obvious that being observant is a critical component of academic writing.

7) CONCLUSION

Academic writing is proving to be an important part of my life. I have gathered building blocks at various points. Albeit, merging helpful guides picked from various sources has been a challenge. I feel quite delighted to realize that the ACA-401D period-one materials have virtually filled this gap. Several aspects of effective academic writing were covered such as essay writing, plagiarism, use of styles, plagiarism, as well as the use of citations and quotations. I found the chapter which provided the distinction between SAE and SBE very helpful. The crib sheet provided several useful information that helped to dispel some of the things that had been quite confusing to me. There is absolutely no way my academic writing skill would not be tremendously impacted by these ACA-401D resources. I look forward to a promising academic career as a doctoral student at EUCLID.

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